

Supporting Information for: Understanding the Anomalous Diffusion of Water in Aqueous Electrolytes Using Machine Learned Potentials

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S1 Machine Learned Potentials (MLPs)

S1.1 Choosing the XC functional

In this work, we chose the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) based revised Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof exchange correlation functional¹ to train the neural network based deep potentials.²⁻⁴ Additionally, Grimme’s D3 dispersion correction was also added to account for the London dispersion interactions.⁵ We refer to this setup as revPBE-D3 consistent with previous literature.⁶ The following benchmarks (our work and from literature) informed our decision to use revPBE-D3 for aqueous solutions.

Benchmarks in this work:

1. Densities of pure water, NaCl and CsI aqueous solutions obtained from revPBE-D3 based DPMD simulations were within 3% of the corresponding experimental values. We note here that various concentrations of aqueous solutions ranging from 0.1 m to 5.5 m were studied (see section S2.1).
2. The hexagonal ice (Ih) was also simulated using DPMD even though ice snapshots were not included in the training set. The densities of the ice phase over a range of temperatures from DPMD were within 3% of the corresponding experimental values. The density difference between water and ice phases at 273 K from our DPMD simulations is about 7% which is close to the experimental value of 9% (see section S2.1). Piaggi et al reported a density difference of 6% from SCAN based DPMD simulations.⁷
3. The water structure at 300 K from our DPMD simulations was compared with that of experiment using oxygen-oxygen radial distribution function $g(r)$. The first peak position and the first minima positions are in very close agreement with the corresponding experimental values (see section S2.2). This observation is consistent with the study by Mundy and co-workers using revPBE-D3 based *ab initio* molecular dynamics simulations.⁶

4. Our DPMD simulations showed good agreement with the experimentally determined neutron structure factor of 2.3 m CsI solution (see main text).
5. Our DPMD simulations showed qualitative agreement with the experimentally determined neutron structure factor of NaCl solutions at various concentrations (see main text).
6. The diffusivity D_∞ of water molecules in pure water from our DPMD simulations ($2.31 \times 10^{-5} \text{cm}^2/\text{s}$) was within 5% of the corresponding experimental value ($2.299 \times 10^{-5} \text{cm}^2/\text{s}$) at 300 K.
7. The shear viscosity of pure water from our DPMD simulations (0.90 cP) was within 5% of the corresponding experimental value (0.89 cP) at 300 K.

Benchmarks from literature:

1. Parrinello and co-workers used revPBE-D3 based *ab initio* molecular dynamics simulations to qualitatively capture the anomalous diffusion by comparing 3 M NaCl and CsI aqueous solutions.⁸
2. Recently (November 2022), Michaelides and co-workers used revPBE-D3 based neural network potentials to study the dissolution of NaCl crystals in its aqueous solution.⁹ They compared the intermolecular structure of NaCl aqueous solutions using revPBE-D3 and SCAN functionals and concluded that both show similar levels of accuracy. They note that while revPBE-D3 shows a 0.1 Å shift to larger distances in the Na-O $g(r)$ first peak position, SCAN functional overstructures O-O $g(r)$. Finally they choose revPBE-D3 due to its lower computational cost (thrice lower) when compared to SCAN.

We also note that other functionals on the higher rungs of the Jacob’s ladder like metaGGA (ex: r²SCAN+rVV10), hybrid functionals (ex: revPBE0-D3 or SCAN0), density corrected SCAN **might** (not always guaranteed) give more accurate representations of

aqueous solutions. However, they are also more computationally expensive (3-20 times more costly than revPBE-D3) thereby preventing their use in large simulation boxes. Large system sizes are necessary to study phenomena at the liquid-air interface or the liquid-crystal interface, which we plan to pursue in the near future. Finally, all the above considerations led us to choose revPBE-D3 functional in our study.

S1.2 Deep potential details

In this work, we developed two machine learned potentials (MLPs) to study NaCl, CsI aqueous solutions called NaClNNP and CsINNPN respectively. We use the deep potential smooth edition (DeepPot-SE) to represent the condensed phase potential energy surface of the aqueous electrolytes. In this framework, the total energy of a snapshot (with periodic boundary conditions) is the sum of atomic contributions which are learnt using deep neural network (called fitting network) architecture. The input to these neural networks are the local atom embeddings which are again learnt on-the-fly using another neural network (called embedding network) with built-in physical symmetries. Another important feature of the DeepPot-SE is the availability of analytic derivatives of energy through which atom-forces and virial can be computed inexpensively.

We use the “two-atom embedding descriptor” with a spherical cutoff of 6 Å and a three layer embedding network with [25,50,100] hidden layers respectively to produce the local atom embeddings. A fitting network of three hidden layers of size [250,250,250] was used. An L2 loss function with a weighted sum of energy, force and virial errors was used to train the neural networks. The weights (energy:force:virial) were modified during the training process starting from 0.02:1000:0.02 to 8:1:8, thereby giving more weight to force errors at the start of the training process. The neural networks were trained for at least 200,000 steps (up to 2,000,000 steps) using Adam optimizer with a learning rate following an exponential decay schedule. Similar parameters have been used to develop machine learned potentials for a wide variety of systems like aqueous solutions,^{10,11} ice-water,^{7,12-14} molten alkali carbonate-

hydroxide electrolytes,¹⁵ and many others.¹⁶

S1.3 Selecting configurations for DFT calculations

We use an active learning approach similar to that of the DP-GEN framework to select the condensed phase configurations to be included in the training/test datasets. Basically, active learning is an iterative approach in which the MLPs are iteratively updated with most relevant configurations that can improve their performance. Details of the three major steps in active learning are outlined below:

Step 0: Initial data: The dataset used to train the first iteration of MLPs were obtained using ab initio molecular dynamics (AIMD) simulations and DFT calculations of classical molecular dynamics simulations. First, AIMD simulations of three systems - neat water, NaCl, and CsI aqueous solutions were simulated as described later (see section S1.3.2). Some $\sim 20,000$ snapshots randomly selected from these four runs were used to create the initial training datasets of the MLPs. Second, classical MD simulations using Madrid-2019 nonpolarizable forcefield were used to sample ~ 4000 condensed phase configurations. Subsequently, the total energies, atomic forces, and virials of these configurations were obtained using DFT based single point energy calculations, the details of which are listed in section S1.3.1.

Step 1: Training: After obtaining the initial dataset, four MLPs with the same architecture were trained on it. The only differences among these four MLPs are the initial weights of the neural networks which were initialized using different random seeds. These four MLPs form an ensemble (or committee) of neural networks which is necessary for the next step. The training was carried out using Adam method for at least 200,000 steps during which the energy and force errors on the validation set were monitored to ensure convergence.

Step 2: Exploring: Once an ensemble of trained MLPs was obtained from the previous step, various exploratory MD simulations were carried out using them. In each MD simulation, one randomly chosen member of the ensemble was used to estimate the forces to do

the timestepping. The force predictions from all members of the ensemble on this trajectory were used to estimate ζ for each configuration (Equation S1).

$$\zeta = \max \sqrt{\langle |\mathbf{F}_i - \langle \mathbf{F}_i \rangle|^2 \rangle} \quad (\text{S1})$$

Here, \mathbf{F}_i is the force on atom i , and $\langle \rangle$ represents the average over the MLP ensemble. Configurations with $\zeta > 0.15$ were selected to be included in the training/validation sets of the next training iteration. Further, multiple types of exploratory MD runs were carried out in each iteration as listed below:

1. Three NPT simulations at 270, 300, and 330 K respectively
2. Two simulated annealing runs with temperatures going from 300-360 and 300-240 K respectively
3. Simulations with pressure ramped from 1-10000 bar
4. Ion distance scans in which the distance between cation and anion is gradually varied by an external restraining potential
5. Ion-ion distance restrained in the repulsive/overlap region

The above exploratory runs were carried out at various salt concentrations with dilute concentrations (~ 0.5 m) in the initial iterations and going up to ~ 3 m in the later ones. The ion distance scans and the restraint runs were used to sample the ion-ion repulsive region at low distances which are rarely sampled by equilibrium simulations even at high pressures or concentrations. In each iteration ~ 1000 configurations were added to the training set. This process is repeated for about 10 iterations after which the MLPs were used to generate the production runs. At the end of the active learning cycle, an RMSE of ~ 0.7 meV/atom and ~ 0.02 eV/Å on the energies and atomic forces respectively was obtained on the validation set.

S1.3.1 Single point energy (SPE) calculations

All the SPE calculations were carried out using the Quickstep module of the CP2K simulation program.¹⁷ The revised version of the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof GGA exchange-correlation functional was used to treat the valence electrons (revPBE-D3).¹ A triple- ζ valence and polarization (TZV2P) basis set was used for O/H atoms, and molecularly optimized double- ζ (DZVP-MOLOPT-SR-GTH) basis set was used for ions. The core electrons were treated with Geodecker-Teter-Hutter (GTH) norm-conserving pseudopotentials.¹⁸ Grimme’s D3 empirical correction term with a cutoff of 40 Å was also used.⁵ Electron density cutoff of 1200 Ry was used to obtain a converged virial.⁶ Also electron density interpolation schemes, which can help the SCF convergence of hybrid/meta-GGA functionals, can have adverse effects on the convergence of virial and hence were not used.⁶ The SCF iterations were considered converged if the energy difference between successive iterations is less than 10^{-7} Hartree.

S1.3.2 Ab initio molecular dynamics (AIMD) simulations

AIMD simulations were carried out to create the training data for the initial iteration of the MLPs and also to benchmark the final MLPs. Three systems were simulated - (i) neat water (64 molecules), (ii) NaCl aqueous solutions (1 Na/Cl + 62 water molecules), and (iii) CsI aqueous solutions (1 Cs/I + 62 water molecules). First the systems were packed at their corresponding experimental density and equilibrated in classical force field framework using the Madrid-2019 force field. Then, four snapshots were selected for each system to run - (i) two independent NPT simulations, and (ii) two independent NVT simulations.

All the AIMD simulations were carried out using the Quickstep module of the CP2K simulation program. The revised version of the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof GGA exchange-correlation functional was used to treat the valence electrons (revPBE-D3). A triple- ζ valence and polarization (TZV2P) basis set was used for O/H atoms, and molecularly optimized double- ζ (DZVP-MOLOPT-SR-GTH) basis set was used for ions. The core electrons were treated with Geodecker-Teter-Hutter (GTH) norm-conserving pseudopotentials. Grimme’s

D3 empirical correction term with a cutoff of 40 Å was also used. Electron density cutoffs of 1200 Ry and 400Ry were used to carry out the NPT and NVT simulations respectively. The large cutoff of 1200 Ry was needed to obtain a converged virial.⁶ The configurations that were sampled for training and validation sets had a density cutoff of 1200 Ry so as to be consistent with the SPE calculations.

The trajectory was evolved using Born-Oppenheimer molecular dynamics with a timestep of 0.5 fs. NPT simulations were carried using the reversible algorithm due to Tuckerman et al¹⁹ at 1 bar and 300 K. The thermostat and barostat timeconstants were set to be ~ 11 fs corresponding to 3000 cm^{-1} . Initially, a “massive” thermostat, .i.e., one thermostat coupled to each degree of freedom, was used to equilibrate the system for about 10 ps. Subsequently, production runs of at least 20 ps were carried out using a “global” thermostat.

S1.3.3 Classical molecular dynamics simulations

Some classical MD simulations were carried out to supplement the exploratory MD runs during the active learning cycles. These were carried out in GROMACS package using the Madrid-2019 force field for the ions and flexible TIP3P force field for the water part.^{20,21}

S2 Benchmarking Machine Learned Potentials

S2.1 Density

S2.1.1 Ice-water density

Table S1: Comparison of density of water and Ice-Ih phases from DPMD to corresponding experimental values. The experimental densities were taken from refs.²²⁻²⁴ All simulations were carried out at a pressure of 1 bar.

Phase	Temperature (K)	DPMD	Experiment	Error (%)
Water	273	0.966(3)	0.99984(1)	-3.4
	283	0.970(3)	0.99970(1)	-3.0
	293	0.972(3)	0.99821(1)	-2.6
	300	0.972(3)	0.99652(1)	-2.5
	310	0.970(3)	0.9922(1)	-2.2
Ice-Ih	273	0.904(2)	0.9167(1)	-1.4
	263	0.906(2)	0.9182(1)	-1.3
	253	0.908(2)	0.9196(1)	-1.3
	233	0.912(2)	0.9222(1)	-1.1

Table S1 compares the density of water and Ice-Ih phases obtained from DPMD to that of experiments. With a maximum error of $\sim 3\%$, observed for liquid water at 273 K, the MLPs developed in this work can be considered to be adequate. Further, the density of water at 300 K obtained in this work (0.972(3)) compares well with the AIMD density reported by Galib et al (0.96(3)) obtained using revPBE-D3/TZV2P functional.⁶ Also, our estimate is close to Niblett et al’s estimate of 0.96 g/cc obtained from long-range ANN based MLPs.¹⁴ At this point, we also note that the equilibrium density of a given XC functional has a sensitive dependence on factors like dispersion correction, basis set, and even the electron density cutoff.^{6,25}

Table S2 compares the density difference between ice-Ih and water phases at 1 bar pressure from our NaCINNP MLP to that of other force field and experimental values. The 7% density difference from our DPMD simulations is close to the experimental value and is similar to that obtained with the SCAN functional. *We also point out that our MLPs were*

Table S2: Density difference upon melting of ice-Ih ($\Delta\rho = (\rho_{water} - \rho_{Ih})/\rho_{Ih}$) at 1 bar pressure. Density difference of the models are reported at their corresponding melting points listed in second column. Density difference from our DPMD simulations (NaClNNP) is reported at 273 K (the experimental melting point), as its melting point is not known.

Model	Temperature (K)	$\Delta\rho$ (%)
this work	273	7
SCAN NNP ⁷	312	6
SCAN DFT ⁷	308	6
TIP4P/ice ²⁶	272	9
TIP4P/2005 ²⁶	252	8
Experiment ²²⁻²⁴	273.15	9

not exposed to ice-Ih configurations during training.

S2.2 Water structure

Table S3 compares the positions of the first two O-O RDF peaks in neat water obtained from our DPMD simulations with corresponding experimental and AIMD values.^{6,27} A near quantitative agreement with both the experiments and AIMD simulations is observed. Also, the two MLPs developed in this work, one each for NaCl and CsI systems, yield nearly identical neat water structure as evidenced by minimal differences in the RDFs (see also SI section S4.1.2).

Table S3: Comparison of the first two peaks of the O-O RDF in neat liquid water at 300 K and 0.997 g/cc (experimental density at 1 bar pressure). The peak details from the two MLPs developed in this work are listed as NaClNNP and CsINNP respectively. The peak positions are listed in Å units. Wherever available, uncertainty in the last digit of the estimate is given in the corresponding parenthesis.

Method	r_{\max}^1	$g(r_{\max}^1)$	r_{\min}^1	$g(r_{\min}^1)$	r_{\max}^2	$g(r_{\max}^2)$	r_{\min}^2	$g(r_{\min}^2)$
NaClNNP	2.80	2.64	3.48	0.83	4.44	1.15	5.56	0.85
CsINNP	2.80	2.61	3.48	0.86	4.50	1.12	5.58	0.86
Experiment ²⁷	2.80(1)	2.57(5)	3.45(4)	0.84(2)	4.5(1)	1.12(2)	5.58	0.88
AIMD-revPBE-D3 ⁶	2.80	2.74	3.45	0.82	-	-	-	-

S2.3 Hydration shell structure

The hydration of alkali-halide ions in water has been extensively studied by classical, ab initio simulations and experiments. Among all the ions, Na and Cl have been the most widely studied with plenty of information available about their hydration structure and number. On the other hand, relatively sparse information is available about Cs and I ions. Here, we present a brief summary of some important contributions in this area with a focus on Na ion and compare them to our DPMD results. For a thorough comparison of hydration structure with different XC functionals, we refer the readers to the following excellent works.²⁸⁻³⁴

S2.3.1 Na-ion hydration

The hydration structure of Na ion has been studied experimentally mainly using X-ray diffraction (XRD), neutron diffraction, and extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) methods.^{31,35,36} In their review, Ohtaki and Radnai summarize the experimental diffraction studies till 1993 and conclude that the Na-H₂O “bond length” falls within the range of 2.4 to 2.5 Å. Further, they estimate the hydration number to be around six. Later, Soper and co-workers used the Empirical Potential Structure Refinement (EPSR) technique on neutron diffraction data of NaCl solutions to extract the Na-O radial distribution function $g(r)$. They find that the position of the first peak of the Na-O RDF occurs around 2.34 ± 0.14 Å, and to be independent of salt concentration. They also estimate the hydration number to be around 4.5 to 5.3 depending on the concentration. In a recent study, Galib et al used a combination of XRD, EXAFS and AIMD simulations to investigate the hydration shell of Na ion. Their estimate of Na-O distance is around 2.38 Å and only slightly larger than Soper’s estimate. They also report a hydration number of 5.5 ± 0.3 from XRD measurements.

From ab initio simulations point of view, Na hydration has been investigated using a wide range of DFT functionals and also many-body force fields. The results vary depending on the choice of the XC functional,²⁹ the dispersion correction term,³⁷ and to a lesser extent

the basis sets and pseudopotentials.³¹ Bankura et al studied the hydration structure of Na ion using various van der Waals (vdW), BLYP GGA density functionals and found that inclusion of dispersion significantly improves their coordination number predictions.²⁹ Galib et al have found that, even though the neat water structure was predicted very accurately by the revPBE-D3 functional, it overestimates the Na-O distance by about 0.15 Å (see figure S1). Similar observations have been made by other works.^{9,32,34} Also, such behavior of overestimating the cation-O distance was found to be common to other cations as well.^{34,38} The higher cation-O distance predicted by the revPBE-D3 functional also results in a softer (more disordered) solvation shell. Despite this limitation revPBE functional has been popular in studying aqueous solutions due to low computational expense.^{9,38} To improve the accuracy without increasing the computational cost, Duignan et al proposed adding a pairwise correction term to overcome this issue and were able to match the experimental RDFs of Na and K ions.³⁸ Recently, Kostal et al proposed much simpler fix by removing the empirical D3 term only for the ion-O interactions and were able to achieve reasonable match with experiments.³⁷

Table S4: Comparison of the first peak of Na-O RDF from various simulations and experiments. The distances are reported in Å. Wherever available, uncertainty in the last digit of the estimate is given in the corresponding parenthesis.

Model	r_{\max}^1	$g(r_{\max}^1)$	r_{\min}^1	$g(r_{\min}^1)$	hydration number
this work	2.50(2)	4.13	3.36(2)	0.32	6.0 at 3.34 Å
AIMD-revPBE-D3 ⁸	2.55	4.28	3.4	0.30	6.2 at 3.40 Å
AIMD-revPBE-D3 ³¹	2.53	4.7	-	-	6.0 at 3.40 Å
AIMD-revPBE-D3 ³⁴	2.50	4.14	-	-	6.1
AIMD-revPBE ³¹	2.45	5.2	-	-	5.7 at 3.40 Å
AIMD-PBE ²⁸	2.42(1)	-	3.26	-	5.3(5) at 3.27 Å
AIMD-PBE0 ²⁸	2.41(3)	-	3.27	-	5.3(2) at 3.26 Å
AIMD-BLYP ³¹	2.40	-	-	-	-
AIMD-BLYP-D2 ³¹	2.46	-	-	-	-
AIMD-SCAN ⁹	2.36	5.79(8)	-	-	-
AIMD-SCAN ³⁴	2.38	6.18	-	-	5.48
Many body ³⁹	2.35	6.44	3.13	0.13	-
Classical (JC) ³¹	2.39	-	-	-	5.5
Classical (Madrid-2019) ^{20,21}	2.34	7.37	3.16	0.16	5.70(2) at 3.16 Å
Exp. (EPSR) ³⁶	2.34	7.4	3.2	0.17	5.3(8) at 3.20 Å
Exp. (EXAFS) ³¹	2.37(2)	-	-	-	5(1)
Exp. (XRD) ³¹	2.381(5)	-	-	-	5.9(6)
Exp. ³⁵	2.41-2.50	-	-	-	6

Figure S1: Comparison of Na-O radial distribution function (RDF) obtained from our DPMD simulations to those from relevant literature reports. The DPMD simulations were of 0.1 m NaCl system carried out at 300 K and experimental density. The red dashed line corresponds to Na-O RDF from AIMD simulations (using revPBE-D3 XC functional) of 3 M NaCl aqueous solutions at 300 K, taken from the work of Parrinello and co-workers.⁸ The blue circles correspond to Na-O RDF from MD simulations (using MB-nrg many body force field) of Na ion in water at 298 K, taken from the work of Paesani and co-workers.³⁹ The orange triangles correspond to Na-O RDF from AIMD simulations (using SCAN XC functional) of Na ion in water at 300 K, taken from the work of Duignan et al.³² The green line corresponds to Na-O RDF from EPSR fits to the neutron diffraction data of NaCl aqueous solutions, taken from the work of Soper and co-workers.³⁶ The inset shows the region of Na-O RDF near its first peak. The green shaded area in the inset corresponds to the range of Na-O distances suggested by Ohtaki and Radnai in their summary of diffraction experiments till 1993.³⁵

S2.3.2 Cl-ion hydration

Figure S2: Comparison of Cl-O radial distribution function (RDF) obtained from our DPMD simulations to those from relevant literature reports. The DPMD simulations were of 0.1 m NaCl system carried out at 300 K and experimental density. The red dashed line corresponds to Cl-O RDF from AIMD simulations (using revPBE-D3 XC functional) of 3 M NaCl aqueous solutions at 300 K, taken from the work of Parrinello and co-workers.⁸ The blue circles correspond to Cl-O RDF from path integral MD simulations (using MB-nrg many body force field) of Cl ion in water at 298 K, taken from the work of Paesani and co-workers.⁴⁰ The orange triangles correspond to Cl-O RDF from AIMD simulations (using SCAN XC functional) of Cl ion in water at 300 K, taken from the work of DelloStritto et al.³³ The green line corresponds to Cl-O RDF from EPSR fits to the neutron diffraction data of NaCl aqueous solutions, taken from the work of Soper and co-workers.³⁶ The inset shows the region of Cl-O RDF near its first peak. The green shaded area in the inset corresponds to the range of Cl-O distances suggested by Ohtaki and Radnai in their summary of diffraction experiments till 1993.³⁵

S2.3.3 Cs-ion hydration

Figure S3: Comparison of Cs-O radial distribution function (RDF) obtained from our DPMD simulations to those from relevant literature reports. The DPMD simulations were of 0.1 m CsI system carried out at 300 K and experimental density. The red dashed line corresponds to Cs-O RDF from AIMD simulations (using revPBE-D3 XC functional) of 3 M CsI aqueous solutions at 300 K, taken from the work of Parrinello and co-workers.⁸ The blue circles correspond to Cs-O RDF from path integral MD simulations (using MB-nrg many body force field) of Cs ion in water at 298 K, taken from the work of Paesani and co-workers.⁴¹ The inset shows the region of Cs-O RDF near its first peak. The green shaded area in the inset corresponds to the range of Cs-O distances suggested by Ohtaki and Radnai in their summary of diffraction experiments till 1993.³⁵

S2.3.4 I-ion hydration

Figure S4: Comparison of I-O radial distribution function (RDF) obtained from our DPMD simulations to those from relevant literature reports. The DPMD simulations were of 0.1 m CsI system carried out at 300 K and experimental density. The red dashed line corresponds to I-O RDF from AIMD simulations (using revPBE-D3 XC functional) of 3 M CsI aqueous solutions at 300 K, taken from the work of Parrinello and co-workers.⁸ The blue circles correspond to I-O RDF from MD simulations (using MB-nrg many body force field) of I ion in water at 298 K, taken from the work of Paesani and co-workers.⁴² The inset shows the region of I-O RDF near its first peak. The green shaded area in the inset corresponds to the range of I-O distances suggested by Ohtaki and Radnai in their summary of diffraction experiments till 1993.³⁵

S2.3.5 Orientation of water in hydration shells

Figure S5: Angular distribution of the water molecules in the hydration shells of ions obtained from DPMD simulations of 3 m NaCl and CsI solutions at 300 K and experimental density. The angle is defined between O-ion and O-p vectors, where O-p is the bisector of the HOH angle of the selected water molecule. The radial cutoffs used to select hydration water are listed in table S11, and are similar to the values used by Parrinello and co-workers in their AIMD simulations of 3 M NaCl and CsI solutions.⁸

S2.4 Transport properties

S2.4.1 Viscosity B-coefficients

The concentration dependence of shear viscosity (η) of aqueous electrolytes is captured well by the Jones-Dole equation, which is an expansion of the relative viscosity (η/η_0) in the powers of concentration (c) (Equation S2).⁴³

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + Ac^{1/2} + Bc + Dc^2 \tag{S2}$$

The A-coefficients do not vary much with the type of ions⁴⁴ and can be calculated theoretically using Debye-Hückel-Onsager-Falkenhagen theory.⁴⁶ On the other hand, B-coefficients vary significantly with ions with positive values corresponding to kosmotropes and negative

Table S5: The experimental Jones-Dole B-coefficients of the ions studied in this work.

Ion	B-coefficient	
	ref ⁴⁴	ref ⁴⁵
Na ⁺	0.086	0.085
Cs ⁺	-0.045	-0.047
Cl ⁻	-0.007	-0.005
I ⁻	-0.068	-0.073

values corresponding to chaotropes.⁴⁵ B-coefficients are also considered to be a measure of ion-solvent interactions relative to water-water interactions.⁴⁴ The values of B-coefficients of individual ions can be obtained from the salt's coefficients using various splitting schemes.⁴⁵ Table S5 presents well accepted values of B-coefficients of Na, Cl, Cs, and I ions at 298 K. As expected Na has a high positive value of 0.086 indicating stronger Na-H₂O interactions when compared to H₂O-H₂O interactions in neat water. On the other hand, Cs/I ions have negative values indicating weaker ion-H₂O interactions when compared to H₂O-H₂O interactions in neat water. Finally, although chloride ion has a negative B-coefficient, its magnitude is low, indicating that Cl-H₂O interactions are similar to H₂O-H₂O interactions.

S3 Estimating Properties from MD

S3.1 Density

Within NPFF, the equilibrium density of liquid phase solutions was obtained from isothermal-isobaric ensemble (NPT) simulations with an isotropic barostat. First, ions and water molecules were packed into a relatively large box using PACKMOL package.⁴⁷ After an energy minimization step to remove hard contacts, a high temperature (500 K) annealing run was carried out in NPT ensemble with Nosé-Hoover thermostat and Berendsen barostat for at least 2 ns.^{48–50} This step is helpful in preventing ion aggregation especially at high concentrations, which is a well-known artifact of non-polarizable force fields with unit charges on ions.⁸ Subsequently, a 5 ns production run was used to estimate the density. Nosé-Hoover thermostat and Parrinello-Rahman barostat (as implemented in GROMACS), with time constants of 2.0 ps, were used in the production runs.^{48,49,51} All NPFF simulations were carried out in GROMACS molecular dynamics package.⁵²

Within DPMD, the equilibrium density of liquid phase solutions was obtained from isothermal-isobaric ensemble (NPT) simulations with an isotropic barostat. Nosé-Hoover thermostat and barostat (as implemented in LAMMPS), with time constants of 0.5 and 1.0 ps respectively, were used to control the temperature and pressure respectively.^{51,53,54} The initial configurations were taken from the corresponding NPFF simulations. Four independent production runs of 1 ns, each with an equilibration of 200 ps, were used to estimate the density. All DPMD simulations were carried out using LAMMPS patched with DeepMD-kit.^{2,55}

S3.1.1 Ice-Ih density

The equilibrium density of ice-Ih phase was obtained from isothermal-isobaric ensemble (NPT) simulations with a fully anisotropic barostat. A rectangular simulation box was packed with 128 water molecules at a density of 0.92 g/cc while preserving the symmetry

using Genice2 package.^{56,57} The package also takes care of proton disorder present in ice-Ih phase. After an energy minimization, the temperature was ramped from 5 K to the target temperature in 100 ps in NVT ensemble. Subsequently, four independent production runs of 100 ps, each with an equilibration of 100 ps, were used to estimate the density at the target temperature. Nosé-Hoover thermostat and barostat (as implemented in LAMMPS), with time constants of 0.5 and 1.0 ps respectively, were used to control the temperature and pressure respectively.

S3.2 Neutron structure factor

The total neutron structure factor $F^N(Q)$ of aqueous CsI solutions was computed from DPMD simulations using eq S3, and compared to the corresponding structure factor from the experiments by Mile et al.⁵⁸ Here, x_α , b_α are the mole fraction and neutron scattering length of species α respectively. Further, ρ is the number density, $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$ is the radial distribution function between the species α and β . A similar expression was used by Mile et al. to compute the structure factor of CsI aqueous solutions using reverse Monte Carlo models.⁵⁸

$$F^N(Q) = 4\pi\rho \sum_{\alpha} \sum_{\beta} x_{\alpha}x_{\beta}b_{\alpha}b_{\beta} \int_0^{\infty} r^2(g_{\alpha\beta}(r) - 1) \frac{\sin(Qr)}{Qr} dr \quad (\text{S3})$$

The partial structure factors $S_{xx}(Q)$ of aqueous NaCl solutions were computed from DPMD simulations using equations S4-S7, and compared to the corresponding structure factors from the experiments by Soper and co-workers.³⁶

$$S_{xx}(Q) = \frac{\sum_{\alpha \neq H} \sum_{\beta \neq H} c_{\alpha}c_{\beta}b_{\alpha}b_{\beta}S_{\alpha\beta}(Q)}{(c_X \langle b_X \rangle)^2} \quad (\text{S4})$$

$$c_X = c_O + c_{Na} + c_{Cl} \quad (\text{S5})$$

$$\langle b_X \rangle = c_O b_O + c_{Na} b_{Na} + c_{Cl} b_{Cl} \quad (\text{S6})$$

$$S_{\alpha\beta}(Q) = 4\pi\rho \int_0^\infty r^2 (g_{\alpha\beta}(r) - 1) \frac{\sin(Qr)}{Qr} dr \quad (\text{S7})$$

Here, c_α , b_α are the mole fraction and neutron scattering length of species α respectively. Further, ρ is the number density, $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$ is the radial distribution function between the species α and β . The neutron scattering lengths were taken from refs.^{36,59}

S3.2.1 System details

Neutron structure factors of the aqueous solutions were obtained from NVT DPMD simulations at 300 K and at their corresponding experimental density. At each concentration, a trajectory of at least 2 ns was used to compute the structure factors. Generally, relatively large simulation boxes are required to capture the low Q features in the structure factor. However, the most prominent peaks in the structure factors of aqueous solutions studied here occur at around 2 \AA^{-1} . Hence, the system sizes used in this work, which can be used to compute structure factor above $Q = 0.5 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, should be appropriate. Moreover, Zhang et al. studied the effect of system size on the structure factors of NaCl solutions and concluded that systems with more than 512 water molecules can capture the main peaks around $Q = 2 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$.¹⁰

Table S6: Details of the DPMD simulation boxes used to obtain neutron structure in this work. The experimental densities of NaCl solutions were taken from ref,⁶⁰ and that of CsI solution was taken from ref.⁵⁸

Salt	c (mol/kg)	$N_{\text{salt}}:N_{\text{water}}$	N_{salt}	N_{water}	box size (\AA)
NaCl	5.5	1:10	51	512	25.79
NaCl	3.3	1:17	30	512	25.39
NaCl	1.4	1:40	13	512	25.08
CsI	2.3	1:24	21	512	26.27

S3.3 Incremental $g(\mathbf{r})$

The radial distribution function or the pair distribution function ($g(\mathbf{r})$) between species x and o is given by Equation S8. Here, V is the volume of the simulation box, N_x and N_o are the number of atoms of x and o species respectively, r_{ij} is the distance between atoms i and j , and $\delta()$ is the one dimensional Dirac delta function.

$$g_{xo}(r) = \frac{V}{N_x N_o 4\pi r^2} \left\langle \sum_i^{N_x} \sum_j^{N_o} \delta(r - r_{ij}) \right\rangle \quad (\text{S8})$$

Similarly, the incremental $g(\mathbf{r})$ (iRDF or $i\text{-}g(\mathbf{r})$) is defined by Equation S9. Where, for every i^{th} x atom, j is selected to be its N^{th} nearest o neighbor. The incremental probability density function (iPDF or $p(\mathbf{r})$), defined by Equation S10, is similar to $i\text{-}g(\mathbf{r})$ except for the normalization factor resulting in the area under each $p(\mathbf{r})$ to be equal to one.

$$g_{xo}^N(r) = \frac{V}{N_x 4\pi r^2} \left\langle \sum_i^{N_x} \delta(r - r_{ij}) \right\rangle \quad (\text{S9})$$

$$p_{xo}^N(r) = \frac{1}{N_x} \left\langle \sum_i^{N_x} \delta(r - r_{ij}) \right\rangle \quad (\text{S10})$$

Figure S6: The first 20 iRDFs and total RDF of O-O sites obtained from DPMD simulations of neat liquid water at 300 K and experimental density.

As the total $g(\mathbf{r})$ is the sum of $i\text{-}g(\mathbf{r})$ s, they can be used to delineate the peaks into

contributions from specific neighbors and was hence used to study the hydration shells in aqueous solutions.^{31,32,39–42} Figure S6 shows the O-O RDF, obtained from DPMD simulations of liquid water at 300 K, being split into its respective iRDFs. Clearly, the first four O-neighbors contribute to the first RDF peak and the fifth neighbor is located near the first minima. Also, there is a significant overlap between all the O-O iRDFs indicating that the boundary between the first solvation shell and the second is fuzzy. On the other hand, the sparse overlap between the fourth and the fifth O-H iRDFs indicates a clear delineation of the hydrogen bonded atoms from the non hydrogen bonded ones (Figure S7).

Figure S7: The first 20 iRDFs and total RDF of O-H sites obtained from DPMD simulations of neat liquid water at 300 K and experimental density. The peaks at 1 Å correspond to the two covalently bonded hydrogen atoms.

While iRDFs can give qualitative information about the hydration shell, it is difficult to compare them across different RDFs because of the non-trivial normalization. Hence, we use iPDFs to extract quantitative information of the peaks such as the mode, mean, variance, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis. Further, Figures S8, S9, and S10 show that the qualitative trends in iRDFs are retained in the corresponding iPDFs across O-O, cation-O, anion-O and anion-H pairs. For instance, the split in the sixth and the seventh iRDFs of Na-O pair is also captured in the corresponding iPDFs. Hence, all the subsequent analysis of the nearest neighbor structure is based on iPDFs.

Figure S8: Top row: The first 16 iRDFs of O-O, Cs-O, and Na-O sites obtained from DPMD simulations of neat liquid water, 3 m CsI, and 3 m NaCl aqueous solutions respectively at 300 K and experimental densities. Bottom row shows the corresponding iPDFs. The qualitative trends in the iRDF peaks are retained in their corresponding iPDFs. The O-O iRDFs, iPDFs from CsINNP and NaCINNP MLPs are shown as dashed and continuous lines respectively. In most cases, they perfectly overlap and are hence difficult to discern.

Figure S9: Top row: The first 16 iRDFs of O-O, I-O, and Cl-O sites obtained from DPMD simulations of neat liquid water, 3 m CsI, and 3 m NaCl aqueous solutions respectively at 300 K and experimental densities. Bottom row shows the corresponding iPDFs. The qualitative trends in the iRDF peaks are retained in their corresponding iPDFs.

Figure S10: Top row: The first 16 iRDFs of O-O, I-H, and Cl-H sites obtained from DPMD simulations of neat liquid water, 3 m CsI, and 3 m NaCl aqueous solutions respectively at 300 K and experimental densities. Bottom row shows the corresponding iPDFs. The qualitative trends in the iRDF peaks are retained in their corresponding iPDFs.

S3.4 Diffusivity

The self-diffusion coefficients (D) were estimated from the mean squared displacements (MSD) using the Einstein relation (Eq S11).

$$D = \frac{1}{6} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d}{dt} \left\langle \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\mathbf{r}_i(t) - \mathbf{r}_i(0))^2 \right\rangle \quad (\text{S11})$$

Here, N is the number of atoms of the species for which the diffusion coefficient is being calculated, $\mathbf{r}_i(t)$ is the position of atom i at time t and $\langle \rangle$ denotes the averaging over time origins.

S3.4.1 Choosing the time window for a linear fit of MSD

The MSD of most dense liquids shows a ballistic regime ($\text{MSD} \sim t^\beta, \beta = 2$) at short times followed by a plateau regime ($\text{MSD} \sim t^\beta, \beta < 1$) and then the diffusive regime ($\text{MSD} \sim t^\beta, \beta = 1$) at long times. In practice however, the long time behavior of the MSD is dominated by noise due to poor statistics and hence the “middle region” of the MSD is usually used to obtain the diffusion coefficients. Ideally, the “middle region” should be beyond the plateau regime ($\text{MSD} \sim t^\beta, \beta < 1$). The exponent $\beta(t)$ (Eq S12) can be used to identify the diffusive region of the MSD.

$$\beta(t) = \frac{d(\ln(\text{MSD}(t)))}{d(\ln(t))} \quad (\text{S12})$$

Here, $\ln()$ denotes the natural logarithm and $\text{MSD}(t)$ is the mean squared displacement at time t . Figure S11(a) shows the behavior of MSD vs time for the oxygen atoms in neat liquid water obtained from DPMD simulations at 300 K. The log-log plot shows the different β regimes described above. Figure S11(b) shows the $\beta(t)$ starting at values much less than 1 (sub-diffusive regime) and approaching the value 1 (diffusive regime) at about 50 ps. In this work, the time window of 100 to 300 ps was chosen to fit the MSD data to a straight line as indicated in figure S11(b).

Figure S11: (a) Mean squared displacement (MSD) of oxygen atoms in liquid H₂O from 20 independent DPMD simulations at 300 K plotted in log-log scale. The black dashed line with slope=1 is drawn as a guide to the eye. The inset shows the variation of MSD across independent runs from 250 to 280 ps. (b) The time evolution of instantaneous slope $\beta(t)$ shows it approaching $\beta = 1$ in about 50 ps. The green area indicating 5% region about $\beta = 1$ is drawn as a guide to the eye. The time window of 100 to 300 ps was chosen for the linear fits of MSD. (c) MSD of the bootstrap samples obtained from sampling (with replacement) from the 20 independent runs. The inset shows the variation of MSD across bootstrap cycles from 250 to 280 ps. (d) Histogram of diffusivities obtained from 1000 bootstrap cycles. The red vertical line indicates the mean ($2.01 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) and the green region indicates the 95% confidence interval (1.95 to $2.07 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) of the diffusivity.

S3.4.2 Bootstrap procedure

Bootstrap procedure was used to estimate the mean and the confidence interval of diffusivity.^{61,62} The procedure works by sampling N MSDs from the MSDs of N independent runs.

The crucial element is to sample with replacement. This process is repeated over a large number (M) of bootstrap cycles (typically about 1000). In each cycle, the mean MSD over N samples was fitted (over a time window chosen above) to obtain a diffusivity value as shown in figure S11(c). At the end of the procedure, M diffusivity values are obtained as shown in figure S11(d). The mean and the 95 percentile range of this distribution were taken as the mean and the standard error of diffusivity.

S3.4.3 Box size correction

Diffusivity estimated from molecular dynamics simulations with periodic boundary conditions shows a systematic dependence on the box size (L). Hence the diffusivity in the thermodynamic limit needs to be obtained by adding a correction term to the finite box estimate. Equation S13 was proposed by Yeh and Hummer as the form of correction where k_B is the Boltzmann's constant, T is the temperature, η is the shear viscosity of the solution.⁶³ In practice, diffusivity is estimated at various box sizes and extrapolated assuming a $1/L$ dependence.¹³

$$D_\infty = D_L + \frac{2.837298k_B T}{6\pi\eta L} \quad (\text{S13})$$

Figure S12 shows the linear dependence of diffusion coefficients of water with $1/L$. The diffusivities are fitted to a straight line using a uncertainty weighted least squares method as indicated by dashed lines in Figure S12. The y-intercept of these fitted lines give the D_∞ values. We note that the diffusivity of water molecules in pure water is always larger than that in 2 m NaCl solutions at all corresponding box sizes including the D_∞ values (Table S9). This observation is similar to previous findings where D/D_0 ratio was independent of the box size.^{64,65}

Table S7: Ratio of diffusivity of water molecules in 2 m NaCl solutions to that of neat water, at various box sizes. The diffusion coefficient values are listed in $\ast 10^{-5} \text{cm}^2/\text{s}$ units.

N_{water}	D_0	D_{2m}	D_{2m}/D_0
256	1.97	1.87	0.953
512	2.01	1.98	0.985
1024	2.08	2.05	0.985
2048	2.14	2.07	0.966
Extrapolated	2.31	2.24	0.972

Table S8: DPMD NVT simulation details of NaCl aqueous solutions used to estimate diffusion coefficient of water molecules. The mean and standard error (ΔD) of the diffusion coefficient values are listed in $\ast 10^{-5} \text{cm}^2/\text{s}$ units. The standard errors are equal to 2σ (2 times the standard deviation of the bootstrap population) giving a confidence interval of about 95%.

Composition ratio	mol/kg	N_{water}	N_{runs}	D	ΔD
-	0	256	16	1.97	0.04
-	0	512	20	2.01	0.06
-	0	1024	16	2.08	0.04
-	0	2048	16	2.14	0.03
1:28	2	256	16	1.87	0.07
1:28	2	512	20	1.98	0.04
1:28	2	1024	16	2.05	0.04
1:28	2	2048	16	2.07	0.03
1:57	1	512	20	2.02	0.04
1:57	1	512	40	2.03	0.03
1:57	1	512	60	2.03	0.02

Figure S12: Box size dependence of diffusion coefficient of water molecules in pure water (red) and 2 m NaCl solution (blue). The dashed lines indicate the straight line fits to the data and horizontal continuous lines indicate the D_∞ values. A weighted least squares method was used to incorporate the uncertainty in the diffusivity values into the fitting procedure.

S3.4.4 Simulation details

The diffusivity of water molecules were estimated from the MSD of oxygen atoms from DPMD simulations in the NVT ensemble. The NVT simulations of the aqueous solutions were carried out at their corresponding experimental densities to enable a direct comparison across different force fields. The ions and water molecules were packed in a box using PACKMOL package. A series of high temperature annealing runs were carried out using classical force field (madrid-2019/TIP3P) to avoid ion clustering in high concentration solutions. The

final configurations obtained from this procedure were used as the initial configurations of the DPMD NVT simulations. Multiple independent runs were carried out at each concentration and thermodynamic state point details of which are listed in Table S9. Equilibration runs of at least 100 ps were carried out before the production run. The trajectory was saved to file every 0.1 ps.

Table S9: Details of the MD simulations along with the corresponding estimates of the self-diffusion coefficients of water molecules in NaCl and CsI aqueous solutions at 300 K. The mean and standard error (ΔD) of the diffusion coefficient values are listed in $*10^{-5}cm^2/s$ units. The standard errors are equal to 2σ (2 times the standard deviation of the bootstrap population) giving a confidence interval of about 95%.

System	c (mol/kg)	$N_{\text{salt}}:N_{\text{water}}$	N_{salt}	N_{water}	N_{runs}	D	ΔD
	0.0	-	-	512	16	2.32	0.06
CsI	1.0	1:57	9	512	14	2.51	0.04
DPMD	2.0	1:28	18	512	16	2.61	0.05
	3.0	1:18	28	512	13	2.63	0.06
	0.0	-	-	512	20	2.06	0.04
NaCl	1.0	1:57	9	512	20	2.02	0.04
DPMD	2.0	1:28	18	512	20	1.98	0.04
	3.0	1:18	28	512	20	1.95	0.05
NPFF	0.0	-	-	512	320	2.13	0.01
CsI	1.0	1:57	9	512	320	2.01	0.01
NPFF	2.0	1:28	18	512	320	1.96	0.01
	3.0	1:18	28	512	320	1.887	0.009
NaCl	1.0	1:57	9	512	320	1.873	0.01
NPFF	2.0	1:28	18	512	320	1.639	0.009
	3.0	1:18	28	512	320	1.408	0.008

Table S9 shows the mean and the standard error of the diffusivities of water molecules in 1 m NaCl solution obtained using different number of independent runs. It shows that ≈ 60 independent runs of 500 ps length are required to obtain a standard error $\approx 1\%$ of the mean.

S3.5 Shear viscosity

The shear viscosity η of the aqueous solutions was estimated from MD simulations using the corresponding Green-Kubo relation S14. Here, V is the simulation box volume, k_B is

the Boltzmann’s constant, T is the temperature, $\tilde{\mathbf{P}}(t)$ is the symmetric and traceless part of the pressure tensor at time t , $\langle \cdot \rangle$ represents the average over time origins. This formula was originally proposed by Evans et al and uses all six independent components of the pressure tensor thereby improving the statistics.⁶⁶

$$\eta = \frac{V}{10k_B T} \int_0^\infty \langle \tilde{\mathbf{P}}(t) : \tilde{\mathbf{P}}(0) \rangle dt \quad (\text{S14})$$

Even though the running viscosity $\eta(t)$ should ideally converge to the true value, large fluctuations are usually observed at long times due to noise. In most practical cases, this behavior of $\eta(t)$ makes it hard to estimate the converged value of the viscosity.

Table S10: Details of the MD simulations along with the corresponding estimates of the shear viscosity of NaCl and CsI aqueous solutions at 300 K. The mean and the standard error ($\Delta\eta$) of the shear viscosity values are listed in centi-Poise units. The standard errors are equal to 2σ (2 times the standard deviation of the bootstrap population) giving a confidence interval of about 95%.

System	c (mol/kg)	N _{salt} :N _{water}	N _{salt}	N _{water}	N _{runs}	η	$\Delta\eta$
	0.0	-	-	512	16	0.799	0.04
CsI	1.0	1:57	9	512	14	0.744	0.03
DPMD	2.0	1:28	18	512	16	0.724	0.02
	3.0	1:18	28	512	13	0.740	0.03

	0.0	-	-	512	68	0.902	0.02
NaCl	1.0	1:57	9	512	44	0.914	0.03
DPMD	2.0	1:28	18	512	52	0.963	0.04
	3.0	1:18	28	512	24	1.027	0.05

S3.6 Velocity autocorrelation function

The velocity autocorrelation function $C(t)$ (or VACF) was computed from MD simulations using equation S15, where $\mathbf{v}_i(t)$ is the velocity of an atom of species i at time t , and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ represents the ensemble average over all initial times t_0 and particles of same species. The velocity autocorrelation function can be used to get the self-diffusion coefficient of the particles by using equation S16. Moreover, the running diffusivity $D(t)$ (equation S17) can be used to study the short time dynamics of particles. Due to the rapidly varying nature of particle velocities in condensed phases, $C(t)$ has to be computed at a fine time interval spacing typically less than 10 fs. In this work, we compute $C(t)$ using particle velocities stored every 1 fs for a total time of 50 ps. The mean and standard errors (2σ) were computed over 40 independent runs.

$$C_i(t) = \langle \mathbf{v}_i(t_0) \cdot \mathbf{v}_i(t_0 + t) \rangle_{t_0} \quad (\text{S15})$$

$$D = \frac{1}{3} \int_0^\infty C(\tau) d\tau \quad (\text{S16})$$

$$D(t) = \frac{1}{3} \int_0^t C(\tau) d\tau \quad (\text{S17})$$

In order to obtain microscopic insights into water dynamics, the VACF of all water molecules was split into contributions from “hydration”, “buffer”, and “free” water depending on their proximity to ions at time $t = t_0$. Such a partition is meaningful only at short time scales and was used to study local dynamics around ions in some earlier literature reports.^{67,68} The radial cutoffs used to classify the water molecules are obtained from ion-O RDFs and are listed in Table S11. The “hydration” water are further split into cation-solvation, anion-solvation, and mixed-solvation water depending on whether they are within cation shell only, anion shell only or simultaneously in both shells respectively. In order to

better understand the acceleration/retardation of various kinds of water molecules, the ratio of running diffusivity $D(t)$ to that of neat water diffusivity D_0 were analysed (see section S4.3). The D_0 values were estimated separately for the two DPMD models and were taken to be the average over the time range of 20 to 40 ps.

S3.6.1 System details

Table S11: The radial cutoffs used to split water molecules into cation-associated, anion-associated, buffer and free water respectively. For instance, in 0.1 m DPMD simulations, water molecules within 3.40 (3.90) Å of a cation (anion) are associated water, in between 3.40 to 9.40 Å are buffer water, and beyond 9.40 Å are free water. Similar hydration shell cutoffs were used by Parrinello and co-workers in their AIMD study of CsI and NaCl solutions.⁸

System	conc. (mol/kg)	cation-O (Å)	anion-O (Å)	buffer (Å)
DPMD	0.1	3.40	3.90	+6.0
NaCl	1.0	3.40	3.90	+3.0
	3.0	3.40	3.90	+1.0
DPMD	0.1	3.90	4.10	+6.0
CsI	1.0	3.90	4.10	+3.0
	3.0	3.90	4.10	+1.0
NPFF	0.1	3.20	3.70	+6.0
NaCl	1.0	3.20	3.70	+3.0
	3.0	3.20	3.70	+1.0
NPFF	0.1	3.70	3.90	+6.0
CsI	1.0	3.70	3.90	+3.0
	3.0	3.70	3.90	+1.0

S4 Results

S4.1 Hydration shell structure

S4.1.1 Radial distribution functions

Figure S13: Cation-Oxygen radial distribution functions ($g(r)$) of (a) Cs-O, and (b) Na-O from DPMD simulations of CsI and NaCl aqueous solutions at various concentrations. (c) and (d) are the respective $g(r)$ s from NPFF (Madrid-2019 force field^{20,21,26}) simulations. All simulations were carried out at experimental densities at 300 K.

Figure S14: Anion-Oxygen radial distribution functions ($g(r)$) of (a) I-O, and (b) Cl-O from DPMD simulations of CsI and NaCl aqueous solutions at various concentrations. (c) and (d) are the respective $g(r)$ s from NPFF (Madrid-2019 force field^{20,21,26}) simulations. All simulations were carried out at experimental densities at 300 K.

S4.1.2 Incremental PDFs

Figure S15: Top Row: Incremental probability density functions of the first sixteen nearest neighbor O atoms from anions (I/Cl) in 0.1 m aqueous solutions at 300 K obtained from DPMD and NPFF simulations. Bottom Row: The first two central moments of the I-PDFs - variance (σ^2) and the mean ($\langle R \rangle$) plotted against each other. The color of square symbols correspond to the same neighbor as in the plots above. The white squares show the next nine nearest neighbors.

Figure S16: Top Row: Incremental probability density functions of the first sixteen nearest neighbor H atoms from anions (I/Cl) in 0.1 m aqueous solutions at 300 K obtained from DPMD and NPFF simulations. Bottom Row: The first two central moments of the I-PDFs - variance (σ^2) and the mean ($\langle R \rangle$) plotted against each other. The color of square symbols correspond to the same neighbor as in the plots above. The white squares show the next nine nearest neighbors.

Figure S17: The iPDF properties of O-O sites (first column) obtained from DPMD simulations of neat liquid water. The second column shows the iPDF properties of Cs-O and Na-O sites obtained from DPMD simulations of 0.1 m CsI, and 0.1 m NaCl solutions respectively. The third column shows the iPDF properties of Cs/Na-O sites obtained from NPF simulations. In the first column, the properties from NaCINNP and CsINNP MLPs are shown as black circles and green triangles respectively. In the second and third columns, the properties of Cs-O sites are shown as red stars and those of Na-O sites are shown as blue squares. The following properties are shown: mode (first row), mean (second row), standard deviation (third row), skewness (fourth row), kurtosis (fifth row) (see section S3.3). All simulations were carried out at 300 K and corresponding experimental densities.

Figure S18: The iPDF properties of O-O sites (first column) obtained from DPMD simulations of neat liquid water. The second column shows the iPDF properties of I-O and Cl-O sites obtained from DPMD simulations of 0.1 m CsI, and 0.1 m NaCl solutions respectively. The third column shows the iPDF properties of I/Cl-O sites obtained from NPFF simulations. In the first column, the properties from NaCINNP and CsINNP MLPs are shown as black circles and green triangles respectively. In the second and third columns, the properties of I-O sites are shown as red stars and those of Cl-O sites are shown as blue squares. The following properties are shown: mode (first row), mean (second row), standard deviation (third row), skewness (fourth row), kurtosis (fifth row) (see section S3.3). All simulations were carried out at 300 K and corresponding experimental densities.

Figure S19: The iPDF properties of O-H sites (first column) obtained from DPMD simulations of neat liquid water. The second column shows the iPDF properties of I-H and Cl-H sites obtained from DPMD simulations of 0.1 m CsI, and 0.1 m NaCl solutions respectively. The third column shows the iPDF properties of I/Cl-H sites obtained from NPFF simulations. In the first column, the properties from NaCLNNP and CsINNPs are shown as black circles and green triangles respectively. In the second and third columns, the properties of I-H sites are shown as red stars and those of Cl-H sites are shown as blue squares. The following properties are shown: mode (first row), mean (second row), standard deviation (third row), skewness (fourth row), kurtosis (fifth row) (see section S3.3). All simulations were carried out at 300 K and corresponding experimental densities.

S4.1.3 Potential of mean force

Figure S20: Cation-Oxygen potential of mean force (PMF) of (a) Cs-O, and (b) Na-O from DPMD simulations of CsI and NaCl aqueous solutions at various concentrations. All simulations were carried out at experimental densities at 300 K.

Figure S21: Cation-Oxygen potential of mean force (PMF) of (a) Cs-O, and (b) Na-O from NPFF (Madrid-2019 force field^{20,21,26}) simulations of CsI and NaCl aqueous solutions at various concentrations. All simulations were carried out at experimental densities at 300 K.

Figure S22: Anion-Oxygen potential of mean force (PMF) of (a) I-O, and (b) Cl-O from DPMD simulations of CsI and NaCl aqueous solutions at various concentrations. All simulations were carried out at experimental densities at 300 K.

Figure S23: Anion-Oxygen potential of mean force (PMF) of (a) I-O, and (b) Cl-O from NPFF (Madrid-2019 force field^{20,21,26}) simulations of CsI and NaCl aqueous solutions at various concentrations. All simulations were carried out at experimental densities at 300 K.

S4.2 Water structure

S4.2.1 Radial distribution functions

Figure S24: Oxygen-Oxygen radial distribution functions ($g(r)$) from DPMD simulations of (a) CsI and (b) NaCl aqueous solutions at various concentrations. (c) and (d) are the respective $g(r)$ s from NPPF (Madrid-2019 force field) simulations. All simulations were carried out at experimental densities at 300 K.

Figure S25: Oxygen-Oxygen radial distribution functions ($g(r)$) from DPMD simulations of (a) CsI and (b) NaCl aqueous solutions at various concentrations. (c) and (d) are the respective $g(r)$ s from NPFF (Madrid-2019 force field) simulations. All simulations were carried out at experimental densities at 300 K. The plots of 1 m, 2 m, and 3 m are shifted up by two, four, and six units respectively for visual clarity.

S4.3 Water dynamics

Figure S26: Ratio of running diffusivity ($D(t)$) of water molecules in aqueous solutions to the neat water diffusivity (D_0). (a), (b) show the diffusivity ratios of water molecules in 0.1 m CsI and NaCl solutions respectively, obtained from DPMD simulations. (c), (d) show the diffusivity ratios of water molecules in 0.1 m CsI and NaCl solutions respectively, obtained from NPFF simulations. The D/D_0 of various water species are labeled as follows: black lines correspond to all water molecules, red lines indicate free water, blue lines indicate cation-associated water, and green lines indicate anion-associated water. The shaded regions around the colored lines indicate the 95 % confidence interval obtained over 40 independent runs. The solvation shell radii were estimated from the first minima of ion-O RDFs and their values are listed in the SI table S11. The D_0 values were estimated separately for each force field. All simulations used for this analysis were carried out at 300 K and experimental densities.

Figure S26 shows the running diffusivity ratios of various kinds of water molecules in 0.1 m CsI and NaCl solutions from DPMD and NPFF simulations. In DPMD simulations, anion-associated water in both CsI and NaCl solutions have D/D_0 greater than unity and are hence faster than neat water. On the other hand, cation-associated water show contrasting behavior across the two aqueous solutions, with Cs-associated water being as fast as neat water while Na-associated water are clearly much slower. NPFF simulations show a completely different

picture. While both cation and anion-associated water are as fast as neat water in CsI solution, they are much slower in NaCl solution.

S4.3.1 Free water dynamics

Figure S27: Ratio of running diffusivity ($D(t)$) of water molecules in aqueous solutions to the neat water diffusivity (D_0). (a), (b) show the diffusivity ratios of water molecules in 0.1 m CsI and NaCl solutions respectively, obtained from DPMD simulations. (c), (d) show the diffusivity ratios of water molecules in 0.1 m CsI and NaCl solutions respectively, obtained from NPFf simulations. The black lines correspond to 0 m neat water, and dashed red lines indicate free water in 0.1 m aqueous solutions. The shaded regions around the colored lines indicate the 95 % confidence interval obtained over 40 independent runs. The insets show corresponding $D(t)/D_0$ curves at longer times. The solvation shell radii were estimated from the first minima of ion-O RDFs and their values are listed in the SI table S11. The D_0 values were estimated separately for each force field. All simulations used for this analysis were carried out at 300 K and experimental densities.

Figure S27 shows that the diffusivity of “free water” in 0.1 m aqueous solutions is the same as that of neat water (within statistical uncertainties), thereby indicating that the effect of ions on the dynamics of water is limited to the first few solvation shells. It should

also be noted that this trend is observed by both DPMD and NPFF simulations. However, at high concentrations the dynamics of all water molecules would get affected by the ions due to their increased proximity (see Figure S28).

Figure S28: Ratio of running diffusivity ($D(t)$) of water molecules in aqueous solutions to the neat water diffusivity (D_0). (a), (b) show the diffusivity ratios of water molecules in CsI and NaCl solutions respectively, obtained from DPMD simulations. (c), (d) show the diffusivity ratios of water molecules in CsI and NaCl solutions respectively, obtained from NPFF simulations. The D/D_0 of various water species are labeled as follows: black lines correspond to 0 m neat water, dashed blue, orange, and green lines indicate free water in 0.1 m, 1 m, and 3 m solutions respectively. The shaded regions around the colored lines indicate the 95 % confidence interval obtained over 40 independent runs. The insets show corresponding $D(t)/D_0$ curves at longer times. The solvation shell radii were estimated from the first minima of ion-O RDFs and their values are listed in the SI table S11. The D_0 values were estimated separately for each force field. All simulations used for this analysis were carried out at 300 K and experimental densities.

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